

Discussion :

Considering the biguanidino structure (I) for paludrine, the complex formation will take place through the guanidino group

rather than the chlorophenyl group of the molecule. The conductometric titration results plotted in Fig. 1 clearly indicate that paludrine form 2:1 complexes with ferrous sulphate and cobalt chloride. The analytical results correspond to analogous compositions e.g. $(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{Cl})_2\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{Cl})_2\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. It is therefore expected that they will have similar structures as given in (II)

(II) Where M = Fe or Co
and X₂ = SO₄ or Cl₂

Structure (II) is supported by the work of Ray *et al*^{6,7} who have studied transition metal complexes of biguanides and have assigned the structure (III) to the four coordination complexes.

Ghosh and Banerjee⁸ have given similar structure to *p*-anisoyl biguanide complexes of bivalent metals. Spacu⁹ has also described copper halide complex of paludrine having composition $[(\text{Paludrine})_2\text{Cu}]\text{X}_2$.

Structure (II) is further supported by the I.R. absorption bands (which will form part of a later communication) of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-NH-C-NH-C-NH}_2^+$ group at 1290 and 1280 cm^{-1} in iron and cobalt complexes. The characteristic absorption bands of $-\text{NH}_2$ are observed at 1735 ± 5 and $2910 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Coordinated water in these complexes is indicated by absorption bands at 815, 1650 and 3400 cm^{-1} .

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Cadmium (II) Complexes with 4-Cyanopyridine

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AS a part of investigations on nitrogen bonded complexes of *d*¹⁰ metals, several complexes of cadmium (II) and zinc (II) have been reported¹⁻⁵ with substituted pyridines and quinolines. This communication describes some cadmium complexes of the general formula $[\text{CdL}_2\text{X}_2]$ where L is 4-cyanopyridine and X is Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻ and NCS⁻. The ligand 4-cyanopyridine has been chosen because it has been reported earlier that cyanopyridines may coordinate either through pyridine nitrogen or through nitrile nitrogen.

Experimental :

All the chemicals used were of *AnalaR* quality. The compounds were prepared in ethanolic medium by reacting cadmium salts, CdX_2 where X is Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻ and NCS⁻ and the ligand in 1 : 2 ratio. There

NOTES

was an almost immediate formation of the compounds which were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. Purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating metal and halogen or thiocyanate by standard methods. The conductance measurements were carried out in acetone medium using a Toshinwal Conductance Bridge. Infrared spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using a Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. The analytical and conductance data are recorded in Table 1, and spectral data in Table 2.

to a lower frequency. This is not observed in the 4-cyano pyridine complexes reported now (Table 2) and on the other hand, there is a slight shift to a higher frequency. So the bonding has presumably taken place through pyridine nitrogen.

The absorption bands attributable to $\nu(\text{C-N})$ and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ in case of thiocyanate complex are recorded in Table 2. The $\nu(\text{C-N})$ and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ are near about 2060 and 810 cm^{-1} respectively (Table-2) indicative of N-bonded terminal thiocyanate group. Hence, all

TABLE 1. ANALYSES, MELTING POINT, AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF CADMIUM(II) COMPLEXES

Compounds	Colour and form	M.P. in ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Conductance (mhos)	% Cadmium		% halogen on thiocyanate	
				Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
$\text{CdCl}_2(4\text{-CN.py})_2$	White crystalline	260	10	28.61	28.72	17.95	18.14
$\text{CdBr}_2(4\text{-CN.py})_2$	„	260	12.5	23.15	23.41	33.14	33.29
$\text{CdI}_2(4\text{-CN.py})_2$	„	220	14	19.32	19.57	44.05	44.23
$\text{Cd(NCS)}_2(4\text{-CN.py})_2$	„	210	14.5	25.46	25.76	26.24	26.60

TABLE 2. INFRARED SPECTRA OF CADMIUM (II) COMPLEXES (Cm^{-1}).

Compounds	$\nu(\text{C-C}) + \nu(\text{C-N})$	$\nu(\text{C-C})$	$\nu(\text{C-C}) + \delta(\text{C-H})$	Thiocyanate	
				$\nu(\text{C-S})$	$\nu(\text{C-N})$
4-Cyanopyridine	1546W	1594S	1205S	—	—
$\text{CdCl}_2(4\text{-CN.py})_2$	1550S	1600VS	1210VS	—	—
$\text{CdBr}_2(4\text{-CN.py})_2$	1550S	1610VS	1210VS	—	—
$\text{CdI}_2(4\text{-CN.py})_2$	1555S	1615VS	1210VS	—	—
$\text{Cd(NCS)}_2(4\text{-CN.py})_2$	1550S	1620VS	1215VS	810VS	2060VS

Results and Discussion :

The complexes reported in the present investigation have a general composition $[\text{CdL}_2\text{X}_2]$ from analysis. All the compounds are white crystalline solids, have low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium they are nonelectrolytes, Λ_M values being of the order of 10-16 mhos (Table 1). Infrared spectra show that most of the absorption bands due to free ligands are modified in the respective complexes indicating bonding to the metal ion.

The ligand 4-cyanopyridine is particularly interesting since it can be bonded to the metal either through the pyridine nitrogen or through the nitrile nitrogen. The preparation and infrared examination of 2,3-, and 4-cyano pyridine complexes of Cu(I), Ag(I) and Au(I) have earlier been reported⁶. It was concluded that in 3- and 4-cyano pyridine complexes, the metals were bound to the pyridine nitrogen and in 2-cyano pyridine complex the bonding was through the nitrile nitrogen. In the present case, had the bonding taken place through the nitrile nitrogen then the band at 1546 cm^{-1} in the free ligand attributed to $\nu(\text{C-C}) + \nu(\text{C-N})$ should have shifted

the complexes reported in the present investigation are four coordinated, presumably having a tetrahedral configuration.

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